

Effect of Solvent on the Stability of some Novel Binuclear Complexes formed by *trans*-[Co(en)₂ClglyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clβ-alaH]²⁺ with few Transition Metal Ions

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The medium effect on the stability constant ($\log K$) of [Co(en)₂ClglyM]ⁿ⁺ and [Co(en)₂Clβ-alaM]ⁿ⁺ (gly = glycinate, β-ala = β-alaninate, M(II) = Cu, Ni and Co) species has been investigated potentiometrically at 30° and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The dielectric constant of the medium has been varied using methanol-water mixtures (0–60% v/v of MeOH).

The proton-ligand association constant ($\log K_H$) of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clgly]⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clβ-ala]⁺ and the stability constant of mixed metal binuclear complexes of *trans*-[Co(en)₂ClglyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clβ-alaH]²⁺ with divalent metal ions have been evaluated. The proton and metal ion binding site is the unbound primary amine group of cobalt(III) substrate. $\log K_M$ vs $\log K_H$ plots are linear for glycinate and β-alaninate complexes.

Formation of various oxo- and hydroxo-bridged binuclear complexes of metal ions has been investigated¹ but measurement of formation constants of such binuclear species with two different metal ions has been rarely attempted. Recently Canon and Benjarvongkulchai² studied the complex formation of [Co(en)₂(OH)₂]⁺ with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn and reported the formation constants of the respective hydroxo-bridge binuclear complexes. This prompted us to determine the stability constants of the binuclear species [Co(en)₂ClglyM]ⁿ⁺ and [Co(en)₂Clβ-alaM]ⁿ⁺ and also the proton-ligand association constant of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clgly]⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clβ-ala]⁺ in methanol-water mixtures of varying composition.

Results and Discussion

The complexation equilibria was studied between 25 and 40° with [chloroglycinato]_T = 3×10^{-3} , [H⁺] = $4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. A time period of ~30 min was needed to study each set of experiment. The spectral scan (O.D vs λ plot, time 0 and 85 min, at

30°) indicates that the change in O.D of the complex at 575, 446 or at 367 nm is only 0.002. So the change in O.D after 30 min will be very very small, which indicates that the extent of aquation is negligible under the experimental condition. The aquation rate of chloroglycinato complex at 50° has been found to be $2.58 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Therefore no complication from aquation is expected.

In order to know that the coordination of the amino acid to pentaamminecobalt(III) moiety takes place through oxygen, the ir spectra of the complexes were taken, the spectra shows sharp C=O stretching band at 1630–1635 cm⁻¹ consistent with the presence of coordinated carboxylate group.

From the pH titration data, values of the acidity constants of *trans*-[Co(en)₂ClglyH]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clβ-alaH]²⁺ were obtained by the method of Irving and Rossotti³. The acid dissociation equilibrium of the *N*-protonated glycinate and β-alaninate complexes are given by equations (1) and (2) respectively,

The values of \bar{n}_A (average number of protons bound per Co^{III} complex by the amino function) were evaluated at various pH values from the

titration curves for complex + HNO_3 and HNO alone using the formula of Irving and Rossotti (Table 1). The stability constants of the binuclear complexes, $\text{trans-[Co(en)}_2\text{ClglyM]}^{3+}$ and $\text{trans-[Co(en)}_2\text{Cl}\beta\text{-alaM]}^{3+}$ ($M(\text{II}) = \text{Co, Ni and Cu}$) for various methanol-water mixtures were calculated with the help of the formation curves (\bar{n} vs pL ; where L denotes the Co^{III} complex and \bar{n} the average number of L bound per $M(\text{II})$ ion). The values of \bar{n} and the exponent pL for the uncomplexed cobalt(III) substrates were calculated from the titration curve for cobalt(III) sub-

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT ($\log K$)^{*} OF COMPLEXES AND FORMATION CONSTANT OF BINUCLEAR COMPLEXES OF Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II}

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$		Vol % (MeOH)						
Temp. °C	Metal ion	0	10	20	30	40	50	60
25	H^+	6.02 (6.07)			6.21 (6.25)			6.41 (6.47)
	Cu^{2+}	3.88 (3.61)			4.09 (3.73)			4.36 (4.03)
	Ni^{2+}	3.39 (3.18)			3.71 (3.35)			3.99 (3.67)
	Co^{2+}	3.16 (2.91)			3.41 (3.15)			3.76 (3.38)
30	H^+	6.04 (6.09)	6.10 (6.15)	6.18 (6.19)	6.25 (6.27)	6.37 (6.40)	6.40 (6.45)	6.44 (6.49)
	Cu^{2+}	3.89 (3.63)	3.97 (3.71)	4.01 (3.74)	4.16 (3.78)	4.29 (3.98)	4.36 (4.05)	4.42 (4.09)
	Ni^{2+}	3.40 (3.20)	3.51 (3.29)	3.64 (3.34)	3.76 (3.43)	3.88 (3.58)	3.94 (3.66)	4.00 (3.71)
	Co^{2+}	3.17 (2.94)	3.25 (3.01)	3.34 (3.04)	3.48 (3.16)	3.58 (3.28)	3.76 (3.35)	3.82 (3.41)
35	H^+	6.05 (6.11)			6.30 (6.30)			6.45 (6.50)
	Cu^{2+}	3.90 (3.68)			4.24 (3.84)			4.46 (4.13)
	Ni^{2+}	3.41 (3.27)			3.82 (3.47)			4.08 (3.73)
	Co^{2+}	3.18 (2.96)			3.55 (3.21)			3.85 (3.43)
40	H^+	6.06 (6.12)			6.34 (6.32)			6.47 (6.52)
	Cu^{2+}	3.91 (3.72)			4.30 (3.88)			4.52 (4.18)
	Ni^{2+}	3.44 (3.30)			3.87 (3.52)			4.10 (3.76)
	Co^{2+}	3.19 (3.00)			3.62 (3.24)			3.90 (3.46)

*Average deviation of $\log K$ values are ± 0.01 ; values in the parenthesis are for $\text{trans-[Co(en)}_2\text{Cl}\beta\text{-ala]}^+$ and unparenthesised values are for $\text{trans-[Co(en)}_2\text{Clgly]}^+$.

strate in the presence of $M(II)$ ions using the formula of Irving and Rossotti⁴ (Table 1).

The values of the overall changes in enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) for the complexation equilibria (Table 2) were calculated using a suitable computer program. The ΔS° values are found less for glycinate complex than that of β -alaninato complex. Coordinated glycine which forms a five-membered chelate (1) is less disordered than β -alanine complex which forms a six-membered chelate ring (2). Therefore, ΔS° for glycinate complex is less favoured in comparison to β -alaninato complex. However, the standard free energy change is more favourable for the glycinate complex than the β -alaninato complex. It is worth noting that the stability of the (1 : 1) binuclear species of $M(II)$ with *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clgly]⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl β -ala]⁺ follow Irving-Williams order : $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II}$. The proton-ligand association constant increases from 6.04 to 6.44 for the chloroglycinato complex, and from 6.09 to 6.49 for the chloro- β -alaninato complex ($I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at 30° when the percentage of methanol in the water-methanol mixture was increased from 0 to 60% (v/v). Values of the dielectric constant of the methanol water mixtures were obtained

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log K_H$ vs $1/D$ at 30° : (A) *trans*-[Co(en)₂Clgly-H]²⁺ and *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl β -alaH]²⁺

from the literature⁵ and were used to construct the plot of $\log K_H$ or $\log K_{M^{2+}}$ vs $(1/D)$ (Figs. 1 and 2). The plots in both the cases were found to be non-linear. The proton ligand as-

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log K_{M^{2+}}$ vs $1/D$ at 30° : (A, B, C) Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} complexes of *trans*-[Co(en)₂Cl β -alaH]⁺ respectively and (D, E, F) Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} complexes of *trans*-[Co(en)₂-Clgly]⁺ respectively.

sociation constant is found to increase with the decrease of the dielectric constant of the medium for both chloroglycinato and chloro- β -alaninato complexes. This is expected because the association of proton with the conjugate base will increase with the decrease of dielectric constant of the medium. The K_H values of chloro- β -alaninato complex are found to be greater than that of the chloroglycinato complex. This is also expected, because in chloro- β -alaninato complex shifting of NH_2 group to beta-carbon makes these protonated amine less acidic than that of the chloroglycinato complex where the NH_2 group is attached to the alpha-carbon atom. This may be perfectly due to the favourable electrostatic repulsion effect of the protonated amine and cobalt(III) centre for glycinate complex.

The formation constant of the binuclear species increases with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. This is perfectly in agreement with the fact that the electrostatic attraction (ion-dipole) between the unbound amino group and M^{n+} ions has the major contribution to the overall free

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXATION EQUILIBRIA OF GLYCINATO AND β -ALANINATO COMPLEXES WITH Co^{II} , Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II}

MeOH % (v/v)	Metal ion	ΔH° kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS° $\text{JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$
0	Cu^{2+}	3.64 \pm 0.04	87.2 \pm 5
		(16.1 \pm 0.6)	(123 \pm 6)
		3.6 \pm 0.3	78 \pm 4
	Ni^{2+}	(15.3 \pm 0.2)	(112 \pm 8)
		3.6 \pm 0.2	73 \pm 6
		(10.3 \pm 0.5)	(90 \pm 3)
30	Cu^{2+}	27.7 \pm 0.7	171 \pm 2
		(18.3 \pm 0.8)	(133 \pm 3)
		21.1 \pm 0.5	141 \pm 2
	Ni^{2+}	(16.9 \pm 0.7)	(121 \pm 5)
		23.0 \pm 0.3	142 \pm 7
		(11.5 \pm 1.0)	(99 \pm 6)
60	Cu^{2+}	18.6 \pm 1	146 \pm 3
		(17.5 \pm 0.9)	(136 \pm 3)
		14.7 \pm 0.3	126 \pm 6
	Ni^{2+}	(10.4 \pm 0.8)	(105 \pm 3)
		15.8 \pm 0.2	128 \pm 7
		(9.4 \pm 0.6)	(103 \pm 2)

*Values in parenthesis are for the β -alaninato complex and unparenthesised values are for the glycinate complex.

energy change associated with the formation of the binuclear species. The formation constant values further reflect that the complexing ability of the half bonded glycine in $\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Clgly}]^+$ is higher than that of β -alanine in $\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}\beta\text{-ala}]^+$ as observed in the corresponding mononuclear metal-ligand chelate complexes due to ring size effect. The glycinate complex forms a five-membered chelate ring (1) with metal ions, whereas β -alaninato complex forms a six-membered chelate ring (2). It is well known that five-membered chelate ring is less strained than six-membered chelate rings, therefore the former is more stable than the latter. The fact that the stability sequence of these binuclear species is opposite to that of the K_H of the corresponding Co^{III} substrates, suggests that the binuclear species have chelate structures 1 and 2 involving the amino group and carboxylate group already bound to cobalt(III) centre.

Experimental

$\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Clgly}]^{2+}$ and $\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}\beta\text{-ala}]^{2+}$ were prepared by reported method⁶ (Found : Co,

12.1; N; 14.2; ϵ_{575} , 48.0; ϵ_{446} , 38.0; ϵ_{367} , 70.0 $\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{ClglyH}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ calcd. for : Co, 12.07, N, 14.3%, ϵ_{575} , 51.0; ϵ_{446} , 34.0; ϵ_{367} , 65.0 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and (Found : Co, 11.57; N, 13.76; ϵ_{580} , 43.5; ϵ_{444} , 37.0, ϵ_{368} , 71.0. $\text{trans}[\text{Co}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}\beta\text{-alaH}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ calcd. for : Co, 11.73; N, 13.9%. Potentiometric measurements were made by a Toshniwal CI-46 pH meter with a glass silver-silver chloride combination electrode. The pH meter was standardised with NBS buffer titration. Then conversion of pH readings to hydrogen ion concentration was done by the method of Van Uitert⁷. Stock solutions of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} nitrate (A.R.) were estimated titrimetrically and also by a Perkin-Elmer 5000 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. A suitable computer program was developed to calculate the proton-ligand association constant and formation constants, using the Irving-Rossotti formula.

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MAZUMDAR & MOHANTY · EFFECT OF SOLVENT ON THE STABILITY OF SOME NOVEL BINUCLEAR COMPLEXES *etc.*

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